

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

THE EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING NATURE-FRIENDLY AND RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN CONDITIONS OF THE RA SEVAN BASIN

Galstyan M.

Doctor of Science, Researcher

Ghukasyan A.G.

Candidate of Science, Researcher

Matevosyan L.

Candidate of Science, Researcher

Scientific center of agriculture of the Republic of Armenia

ABSTRACT

To improve the ecological state of Lake Sevan, as well as to ensure ecologically safe food product it is necessary to deny using mineral fertilizers when implementing fertilization activities in potato fields, and to apply 10t/ha organomix biohumus (7 t/ha) instead, 60 % of which should be introduced in the soil together with sowing process, while 40 % - via feeding. At the same time 3 t/ha zeolite or bentonite with sowing should be entered into the soil and foliar feeding via bioliquid with 500 L water upon 10 L/ha rate should be implemented twice, as a result of which 400-420 c/ha high-quality potato yield, 2026.5 thousand AMD/ha (4239 \$) extra profit can be ensured, at the same time 1300 m³/ha irrigation water is saved, which flowing into Lake Sevan will improve the ecological state of waters creating favorable conditions for the growth and development of flora and fauna.

Keywords: Lake Sevan, organic fertilizers, technologies, zeolite, irrigation regime.

Introduction. Sevan is the only Transcaucasian large lake, which serves as a perspective reservoir for the strategic reserves of drinking water for Armenia and neighboring countries. The role of Lake Sevan is indispensable in the water balance of the republic, as well as in the development of agricultural, energy, industrial and other branches of national economy. The lake level has stayed constant for centuries due to certain balance established between the lake inflow and outflow (28 rivers and streamlets flow into Lake Sevan and only the river Hrazdan originates from Lake Sevan).

The restricted amount of fuel-energy mineral resources, the need for receiving energy powers for the economy development and the issue related to the irrigation of 130 thousand ha land area in the Ararat valley have become a sound background for taking 170-245 mln m³ water from the lake, which entailed to the fall of lake level and to the emergence of multiple ecological problems. The deterioration of the Lake Sevan ecological state is mainly due to industrial and domestic wastewaters, livestock wastes pollution, as well as the occurrence of biogenic elements upon the leaching of mineral fertilizers and pesticides from the soil mass of agroecosystems related to erosion processes [Hayrapetyan E.M., Shirinyan A.V., 2003; Galstyan M.H., 2007, 2018].

Upon the investigations it has been found out that 269 tons of nitrate, 144 tons of nitrite, 105 tons of oil product, 58 tons of phosphate and 2837 tons of fecal matters are annually dumped into Sevan Lake which are serious threats for the regular growth and development of fauna and flora of the lake at the same time causing biogenic contamination (eutrophication) in the lake .

One of the most important ways of solving the ecological issue of Lake Sevan is the increase of water level at the expense of fresh waters, herewith recovering the balance of the lake ecosystem. Being the largest

agricultural zone of the republic, the basin of Lake Sevan is somehow distinguished from other agricultural zones by its physiogeographical conditions, geological structure, soil and climate, as well as water and vegetation cover characteristics. The little amount of precipitations fallen in the basin, particularly in the vegetation period, small amount of organic matters in the soil, high air temperature and systematic winds promote the rapid mineralization of accreted plant residues; insignificant amount of humus is accumulated in the soil and even in case of applying well-developed technologies, under such conditions it is impossible to harvest abundant and high quality yield of the grown crops without availability of nutrients and optimal moisture reserves. Thus, any study aimed at the solution of ecological problems of the waters in Lake Sevan, as well as at the yield capacity increase of the agricultural crops cultivated in the lake basin and the improvement of their qualitative indices, is of paramount significance and actual, meanwhile emanates from the requirements of the strategies developed for the improvement of ecological state in Lake Sevan and for the development of agriculture in the region.

The main goal of improving growing technologies for agricultural crops and particularly for the increase of row-crops yield capacity, its qualitative indices, as well as the decrease of its cost price is to provide maximum yield per unit area. This issue is surely to be solved via efficient use of environmental components, as well as through the application of resource saving and nature-friendly technologies.

For the solution of the mentioned problems, along with multiple factors (introduction of new high yielding varieties, application of methods for combating pests and diseases, improvement of production and sale methods) the scientifically justified application of soil enhancers becomes particularly significant, which can

provide high results with low expenses from the prospect of yield capacity and quality increase, as well as from that of economical use of environmental components and their conservation.

The data of literature indicate that when applying intensive technologies, in order to receive high and sustainable yield from the agricultural crops, including potato, great amount of mineral fertilizers and other chemical means approved upon multiple national and international research works have been used [Mineev V.G. 1990, Galstyan M.H., 2007, 2018].

In this respect the application of alternative methods for agricultural crop cultivation is of prior importance. To this end we have set a task to study and develop new technologies to ensure ecologically safe and high yield from the field crops (potato) grown in terms of irrigated agriculture via regulating nutritional and moisture regime in conditions of the Sevan basin and to promote the rise of the lake water level via the stream of saved irrigation water flowing into Sevan Lake, as well as to promote the balanced growth of flora and fauna species living in the lake and improvement of ecological state in water ecosystem.

Materials and methods. To achieve the mentioned goals, in soil and climatic conditions of the Sevan basin the economic and ecological efficiency of application methods of organic matters, bio-liquid growth stimulant and different particle sizes of natural zeolite endowed with high absorption capacity produced from the household and agricultural wastes through the latest biotechnological methods was evaluated for the first time (2020-2021) via field experiments conducted in the potato fields.

The field experiments were set up in the fluvial-terrace soils (Artsvanist community of Gegharkunik region) characteristic to the Sevan basin; here the prevailing part of potato plantations (82.0 %) is cultivated in the mentioned soils, while 18.0 % is cultivated in the leached black soils.

The reaction of experimental soil medium (pH) fluctuates within 6.7-7.0, in the plowing layer the amount of absorbed cations (Ca^{++} , Mg^{++}) makes 25.2-30.2 mg/eq in 100 g soil. The humus content of the soil makes 4.2 %; they are poor in easy hydrolyzable nitrogen (3.6 mg), contain mid amount of mobile phosphate (5.4 mg), while are well provided with exchangeable potassium (37.0 mg in 100 g soil).

The field experiments were set up in three repetitions and each experimental bed was measured as 30 m² for the following options:

1. Control (without fertilization),
2. Organomix 10 t/ha + zeolite 3 t/ha (with the particle size of 0.75 mm, single application via seeding),
3. Biohumus 7 t/ha + zeolite (0.75 mm) 3 t/ha – single application (via seeding),
4. Organomix 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha – via nutrition + 3 t/ha zeolite (0.25 mm particle size, via seeding),
5. Biohumus 4 t/ha via seeding + 3 t/ha – via nutrition + 3 t/ha zeolite (0.25 mm particle size, via seeding),

6. $\text{N}_{150}\text{P}_{150}\text{K}_{150}$ -the mineral fertilizers' rates accepted and applied (via seeding) in the zone and based on the nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium contents in the organomix and biohumus available in these fertilizers the appropriate rates have been estimated: the content of NPK in organomix and biohumus has made 1.55 and 2.3 % (N), 1.4 and 2.6 % (P_2O_5), 1.6 and 2.9 % (K_2O) respectively.

In 2020 and 2021 potato planting rate made 37.0 and 36.2 c/ha respectively. The studies were conducted on mid-late-ripening potato variety "Marfona" and the further treatments and harvesting activities were implemented per the agricultural rules accepted in the region.

The full rates of biohumus and organomix with adequate doses were implemented for one case with single application via seeding (2nd and 3rd options), for another case they were introduced with split application – via seeding and nutrition in the budding period, as mentioned in the scheme. In the options of applying the mentioned organic fertilizers, zeolite of different particle sizes (0.75 mm and 0.25 mm) with 3 t/ha dose was implemented and, in all variants, double foliage nutrition – in budding and blooming periods – through bio-liquid growth stimulant with 10 l/ha dose (with 500 l water) was carried out [FAO-2004].

In order to assess the soil moisture content and regulate potato irrigation regime by the impact of soil conditioners, in all experimental options sensors of ETg measuring device were installed and by means of calculating directives for every two days, plants watering activities were organized.

The agrochemical properties of the experimental plots and the qualitative indices of the harvested yield were determined through universal methods introduced in the methodical manual of agrochemical analyses published under the editorship of B.A Yagodin [Yagodin, 1989], the yield capacity data were subjected to mathematical analyses upon the determination of experimental error (Ex) and the least significant difference ($\text{LSD}_{0.95, c}$) through the method of dispersion analysis [Dospuchov B.A, 1973].

Results. According to the average data of repeated field experiments the single and split applications of the appropriate organomix and biohumus doses, as well as equal application doses of zeolite with different particle sizes and the bio-liquid growth stimulant have exerted certain effect on the sprouting, growing and development phases of potato. As compared to the control variant (without fertilization), in case of both single and split application of organomix and biohumus the potato sprouting process, as to the average data of the investigation years, was intensified by 3 (in case of organomix) to 5-6 days (in case of biohumus). If in the control variant (without fertilization) the potato tubers (planting material) sprouted after 32-33 days and in the variant where organomix was used it occurred after 29-30 days, then in case of biohumus application the sprouting happened after 26-28 days.

The effect of biohumus and bio-liquid growth stimulant is more vivid in the transitional periods of phenological phases of potato. In the initial stages the effect was not so much observed, while during the final phases (blooming, maturation) the plants vegetation

duration was reduced to a certain extent comparing with the options where bio-liquid and biohumus had been applied. So, if in the control variant the period started from the potato sprouting up to maturation lasted 93-96 days, in the organomix and bio-liquid variant it lasted 88-92 days, then in the options where biohumus (both single and split application) and growth stimulant (foliar nutrition) were applied, the mentioned period lasted 83-87 days, in other words, the vegetation period got reduced by 10-11 days against that of recorded in the control variant and by 5 days as compared to the same index observed in the variant of organomix and growth stimulant application. This circumstance is also important in the sense that there will be an opportunity in the farm households to harvest and store potato yield without any losses, particularly when in the potato harvesting period it often rains and sleets (from the last decade of September up to the first half of October) in the mountainous regions of the republic, including in the basin of Sevan.

Throughout the investigations it has been found out that in the variants where biohumus and organomix (single and split applications), zeolite and growth stimulant were applied, the plants grew up more intensely

(exuberant), had dark green color and increased stem branching and provided dense leaf mass. At the same time, the research results have shown that the split application of biohumus and organomix as compared to the single application with zeolite and bio-liquid has had a more favorable effect on the potato growth and development, as well as on the formation of above- and underground plant organs, ensuring favorable conditions for the increase of potato tuber accumulation index and its yield amount (Table 1).

In the result of single application of organomix and biohumus it has been disclosed that if in this case the daily average tuber accumulation index made 9.4 and 10.6 grams from the budding to the maturation period respectively, then in case of their split application with the same doses this index amounted to 10.2 and 10.7 grams respectively. As the table data indicate, in the options of single and split application of biohumus compared to the equal doses and application times of organomix, the stimulating effect of biohumus was revealed both on the potato tubers formation and tubers accumulation intensity, which surely promoted yield amount increase.

Table 1.
The effect of soil improvers on the potato growth and development, tuber accumulation and yield capacity per the phenophases according to the average data of 2020-2021

n/n	Options	Tubers weight per the developmental phases, g			From budding to ripening		Average potato yield, c/ha		Yield surplus	
		Budding	Blooming	Ripening	day	Average daily tuber accumulation, g	2020	2021	c/ha	%
1	Control (without fertilization)	68,4±4,0	28,0±5,0	433,8±4,5	58	6,3	198,0±6,0	203,0±3,0	200,5	-
2	Organomix 10 t/ha (single application)+ zeolite 3 t/ha (with 0,75 mm particle size via seeding) + bio-liquid – double spraying	70,2±3,0	319,0±3,2	549,6±6,0	51	9,4	324,0±6,9	340,0±6,0	332,0	131,5
3	Biohumus 7 t/ha (single application) + zeolite 3t/ha (with 0,25 mm particle size via seeding) + bio-liquid – 2 (double) sprayings	72,6±4,0	342,0±4,5	570,8±6,5	47	10,6	369,0±7,0	390,0±5,4	379,5	179,0
4	Organomix 6 t/ha (via seeding)+ 4 t/ha via nutrition + zeolite 3 t/ha (0,75 mm particle size via seeding) + bio-liquid - 2 sprayings	72,4±3,6	339,0±5,0	609,8±5,9	52	10,2	375,2±5,2	389,0±7,2	382,1	181,6
5	Biohumus 4 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha via nutrition +zeolite 3 t/ha (with 0,25 mm particle size) + bio-liquid – 2 sprayings	74,4±5,2	349,0±5,4	609,4±6,2	50	10,7	400,0±4,6	442,0±6,6	421,0	220,5
6	N ₁₅₀ P ₁₅₀ K ₁₅₀ via seeding	71,3±6,0	321,6±3,9	595,0±5,4	59	8,9	305,0±5,0	321,4±7,0	313,2	112,7
	EX ₀ %						2,9	3,2		
	LSD 0,95,c						7,8	8,6		

The average data of two-year investigations have shown that if in the variants with single application of equal doses of organomix and mineral fertilizers the potato yield surplus respectively made 131.5 c/ha (65,6 %) and 112.7 c/ha (56,2 %) against the control variant, then in case of the same dose of biohumus application the yield surplus amounted to 179.0 c/ha or 89.3 %, while in case of split application of biohumus the yield surplus, compared to the split application of organomix, made 38.9 c/ha or 19.4 %.

As it has been already mentioned we have used 3 t/ha natural zeolite (for one case with 0.75 mm particle size, for another – 0.25 mm particle size) in the variants of both single and split application of equal doses of organomix and biohumus.

By installing ETg moisture sensors in each fertilization variant and examining the soil moisture level both for the control and fertilized variants every two days, the irrigation activities of potato field were planned and organized. In the variants where zeolite with the rate of 3 t/ha was used, irrespective of its particle size, the plants were watered twice less than in the variants without fertilization (control) and where only mineral fertilizers were applied.

The potato field is watered at least 6 times (watering rate – 650 m³, irrigation rate – 3900 m³/ha) per the agronomic norms and related to the small amounts of precipitations characteristic to the region. In the variants where zeolite on the background of experimented organic fertilizer (irrespective of its application form) was applied the potato field was watered four times and 1300 m³/ha irrigation water was saved, which surely flowed into Lake Sevan promoting the rise of its water level and improvement of its ecological state. Meanwhile, the research results indicated that in the variants where zeolite was used not only was water saved, but also no potato yield decrease was ever observed, moreover yield increase by 9.4-44.4 % was recorded as compared to the variants where equal doses of mineral fertilizers were applied.

Such yield surplus and irrigation water saving resulted from the applied organic fertilizers, growth stimulants and zeolite is mainly related to the composition of the mentioned substances and their adsorption properties. Upon the effect of soil bacteria the organic matters are rapidly decomposed and become affordable nutrients for the plants, while due to the zeolite decomposition again upon the impact of soil bacteria, SiO₂ is derived, which, due to its water absorption capacity, the ability to combine OH groups round its domain and to absorb precipitation waters during the vegetation period and the excess water generated during the irrigation process, later on, in case of moisture shortage, gradually transfer the accumulated humidity to the plants creating favorable conditions for their growth and development. According to the data of some researchers [Galstyan M.A. and others, 2018, Hayrapetyan E., Galstyan M. and others, 2009, Melqonyan K.G and others, 2004], zeolites and natural raw materials belonging to that group, in addition to 14 % crystal

water content, are also able to absorb moisture with the amount of 40-70 % of their total mass. This circumstance and the interpretation provided above about the zeolite water absorption and retention capacity have disclosed that water absorption capacity of fluvial-valley-terrace soils increases from 27.8 % up to 35.4-46.0 % in case of zeolite availability. At the same time the water absorption capacity of coarse-grained zeolite (0.75 mm) amounts to 49.6 %, while that of the fine-grained zeolite (0.25 mm) makes up to 54.6 %.

Laboratory studies have been conducted in order to reveal the maximum water retention capacity of the soil mixture containing different proportions of fine-grained and coarse-grained zeolites. The variants with 12, 18 and 24 % fine-grained and coarse-grained zeolites have been considered. Meanwhile the maximum water retention capacity of fine-grained and coarse-grained zeolite of the investigated experimental plots has been studied individually. The results are summed up in the diagrams below (Diagram 1,2).

Generally, the effect of this or that factor is evaluated not only through the criteria of yield mass, but also by means of such qualitative properties, which make the given food product more utilizable. Upon the results of conducted investigations, it has been found out that the applied soil enhancers have had considerable effect on the potato marketability, average weight of commercial tubers and on the improvement of qualitative indices in general (Table 2). The data of table testify that throughout the two-year investigations the changes in the potato qualitative indices under the impact of soil enhancers (organomix, biohumus, zeolite, bio-liquid, mineral fertilizers) have been recorded with the same patterns. As compared to the control variant (without fertilization) the split applications of biohumus and organomix have exerted more favorable effect on the mentioned indices than the single application of those fertilizers. So, if in case of applying the appropriate doses of organomix and biohumus with the same doses of zeolite and bio-liquid growth stimulant only via seeding the potato marketability increased by 22.4 and 25.7 % respectively against the control variant, then in case of split application of the same doses of the mentioned fertilizers (via seeding and nutrition) the increase in the marketability made 25.7 and 30.7 % respectively. Whereas, in case of applying equal doses of mineral fertilizers, according to the average data of two-year investigations, the marketability increased only by 10.4 %.

Some of the most important criteria for evaluating potato quality are considered to be the contents of dry matters, starch, vitamin C and nitrates in potato. Upon the results of investigations it has been found out that fertilizers of organic origin, growth stimulant bio-liquid and natural raw material zeolite, irrespective of its particle sizes, have provided high potato flavor qualities everywhere, as compared to the same index recorded in the control variant (without fertilization), increasing starch content by 6.8-9.4 % and vitamin C – by 1.6-3.0 mg %.

Table 2.

The effect of soil enhancers/improvers on the marketability of potato tubers, dry matters, starch, vitamin C and nitrate accumulation

n/n	Options	2020				2021				Two-year average data							
		Average yield, c/ha	Tubers per fractions			Marketability, %	Average weight of commercial tubers, g	Average yield, c/ha	Tubers per fractions			Marketability, %	Average weight of commercial tubers, g	Dry matters, %	Starch, %	Vitamin C, mg %	Nitrates, mg/kg
1	Control (without fertilization)	198,0	30,2	33,4	36,4	63,6	61,0	203,0	32,0	34,0	34,0	66,0	63,0	20,6	15,2	10,2	120,0
2	Organomix 10 t/ha (single)+ zeolite 3 t/ha (0,75 mm) via seeding +bio-liquid 5 l/ha 2 sprayings	324,0	45,0	42,6	12,4	87,6	98,0	340,0	43,6	43,2	13,2	86,8	96,6	24,9	22,0	11,8	130,0
3	Biohumus 7 t/ha (single)+zeolite 3t/ha (with 0,25 mm particle size (via seeding) + bio-liquid 5 l/ha 2 sprayings	369,0	60,5	29,7	9,8	90,2	107,0	390,0	61,0	29,8	9,2	90,8	106,2	25,6	23,0	13,0	140,0
4	Organomix 6 t/hu (via seeding)+ 4 t/ha via nutrition + zeolite 3 t/ha (with 0,75 mm particle size via seeding)+bio-liquid 5l/ha 2 sprayings	375,2	59,0	32,0	9,0	91,0	106,5	389,0	62,4	27,6	10,0	90,0	107,0	25,0	22,8	13,0	135,0
5	Biohumus 4 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha via nutrition +zeolite 3 t/ha (0,25 mm)+ bio-liquid 5l/ha 2 sprayings	400,0	70,4	24,1	5,5	94,5	140,0	442,0	74,0	22,4	3,6	96,4	141,5	26,8	24,6	13,2	139,0
6	N ₁₅₀ P ₁₅₀ K ₁₅₀ via seeding	305,0	39,8	34,4	25,8	74,2	82,6	321,4	41,0	35,2	23,8	76,2	87,4	23,8	17,2	10,8	270,0

In the variant where equal doses of mineral fertilizers were applied almost no changes against the control variant were recorded. As a result, if in the control variant the tubers starch content made 15.2 % and vitamin C -10.2 mg%, then in $N_{150}P_{150}K_{150}$ variant these indices made 17.2 % and 10.8 % respectively (Table 2).

The situation is different related to the results of investigations conducted for the nitrates content. Though the nitrate content in potato increased by 10-20 mg/kg in the variants of organic fertilizers and growth stimulant application against the same index recorded in the potato tubers (120 mg/kg) grown in the control

variant and amounted to 130-140 mg/kg, nevertheless the mentioned amount is half as less than the rate of MPC (maximum permissible concentration) set as 250 mg/kg for the potato tubers. Whereas the nitrate content in the potato yield treated with mineral fertilizers is higher than MPC by 20 mg and amounts to 270 mg/kg.

The agro-events become widespread and key study subjects in agriculture when they cause positive ecological changes in functioning of nature components, are economically efficient and every dram spent ensures certain profit, otherwise the given event isn't studied and introduced in the production.

Table 3.

Economic efficiency of applied soil enhancers in the potato plantations

Indicators	Options					
	Control (without fertilization)	Organomix 10 t/ha (single)+ zeolite 3 t/ha (0,75 mm) via seeding + bio-liquid 5 l/ha 2 upulgnuf	Biohumus 7 t/ha (single)+zeolite 3 t/ha (with 0,25 mm particle size (via seeding) + bio-liquid 5 l/ha 2 spray- inos	Organomix 6 t/ha (via seeding)+ 4 t/ha via nutrition + zeolite 3 t/ha (0,75 mm) (via seeding)+bio-liquid 5l/ha 2 sprayings	Biohumus 4 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha via nutrition +zeolite 3 t/ha (0,25 mm)+ bio-liquid 5l/ha 2 sprayings	$N_{150}P_{150}K_{150}$ via seeding
Average yield capacity of the options, c/ha	198,0	324,0	369,0	375,2	400,0	305,0
Yield surplus comparing to the control variant, c/ha	-	131,5	179,0	181,6	220,5	112,7
The cost of yield surplus, thousand AMD	-	1972,5	2685,0	2724,0	3307,5	1690,5
Fertilizers, growth stimulant, zeolite and other related expenses, thousand AMD	-	860,0	1040,0	900,0	1100,0	170,0
Extra yield harvesting, transportation and storing expenses, thousand AMD	-	130,0	179,0	182,0	220,0	113,0
Total expenses, thousand AMD	-	990,0	1219,0	1082,0	1320,0	283,0
Cost of saved irrigation water, thousand AMD	-	39,0	39,0	39,0	39,0	-
Extra profit, thousand AMD	-	1021,5	1544,0	1681,0	2026,5	1407,0
Extra profit per each AMD spent, AMD	-	1,03	1,27	1,55	1,55	4,97

During the conducted investigations, when estimating the economic efficiency of the implemented measures, the current purchase prices set for organomix, biohumus, zeolite, bio-liquid and those set for nitrogeneous, phosphorous and potash fertilizers, as well as the sale price of potato in conditions of the RA market relations were accepted as baseline data.

The calculations have indicated that like the organic fertilizers, the bio-liquid growth stimulant and zeolite have provided high extra profit comparing to the equal application doses of mineral fertilizers and during the vegetation period 2 watering rates of irrigation water per hectare (100 m³/ha) have been saved, which flowed into Lake Sevan promoting the improvement of

ecological state in the lake via the regular growth and development of its fauna and flora (Table 3).

As the table data show, the biohumus has had more favorable effect on the potato growth and development, its yield quantity and quality, as well as on the economic efficiency, than the equal doses of organomix and mineral fertilizers. At the same time, it has been grounded upon the example of potato, that when organizing fertilization activities in the ploughlands of row crops in conditions of Sevan basin, it is necessary to refuse mineral fertilizers and to apply 7 t/ha biohumus instead, out of which 60 % should be introduced in the soil via seeding, 40 % via nutrition; it is also required to simultaneously introduce 3 t/ha zeolite and implement foliar nutrition twice with 10 l/ha

application dose in the budding and blooming period. In case of implementing such a technology, 400-420 c/ha high quality potato yield and 2026.5 thousand AMD extra profit will be ensured. At the same time, by applying the mentioned soil enhancers/improvers 1300 m³/ha irrigation water has been saved in conditions of irrigated agriculture, due to which the socioeconomic conditions of the region's population will be improved and ecological problems of the lake water will find the desired solution.

The investigations carried out in the potato fields have proved that the soil improvers involved in the mentioned technologies have provided more favorable effects on a number of agrobiological indicators against the similar amounts of mineral fertilizers. Their application in the land areas of Sevan basin is indispensable not only from the agronomic but also from environmental standpoint. Substitution of mineral fertilizers and other chemical substances with the safe biological and mineral matters is urgent, first of all for the implementation of the program on the recovery of the integrated ecosystems of Lake Sevan, which is entirely related to the development of the agricultural system applied in the basin, environmental improvement, saving of the irrigation water flowing into the lake and production of ecologically safe food product. It is worth adding, that the mentioned experimented technology was implemented in the two hectares of potato and cabbage fields cultivated by 22 farm and private households in the three communities of Gegharkunik region (basin of

Lake Sevan), as a result of which 420-567 c/ha high quality potato and 550-660 c/ha cabbage yield was harvested. Besides, per the average watering rates determined for the mentioned two crops 1300 and 2000 m³/ha irrigation water was saved, respectively.

Professional extension work related to the technology has been provided by the employees of the research center.

The consulting activities have been conducted among the self-employed farmers and via lectures organized in the Gegharkunik region in form of extension work.

It is worthwhile to mention that the whole sum for purchasing and transportation of 12 tons of organomix, biohumus (5 t), bioliquid (50 L) and zeolite and bentonite (4 tons each) foreseen for 2 ha land areas upon the technological requirements, which is estimated as AMD 2 mln, has been provided by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (GIZ) within the frame of the program "Environmental Protection of Lake Sevan".

The authors of the research work would like to express their acknowledgements to the European Union and German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (GIZ-BMZ) for their joint material support provided within the frame of the program "Environmental Protection of Lake Sevan" (EU4Sevan) to implement field activities and to provide the mentioned amounts of soil improvers to the farmers.

Diagram 1. Water retention capacity of fluvial-valley-terrace soils depending on the size of zeolite particles and its composition by percentage

Diagram .2. The maximum water retention capacity of soil mixture in conditions of different ratio of fine-grained and coarse-grained zeolite content in the soil

Conclusions and recommendations. Summing up the results of experimental works, laboratory investigations, as well as the production investments implemented in the farm households throughout 2020-2021, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The split application (via seeding and nutrition) of appropriate doses of organomix and biohumus on the background of natural raw material zeolite and bio-liquid growth stimulant in the potato fields cultivated on the fluvial terrace soils of Lake Sevan has exerted more favorable effect on the potato growth, development and economic-ecological efficiency than the single application (via seeding) of the similar doses of the mentioned and mineral fertilizers.

2. It has been disclosed that in contrast to the control variant (without fertilization), the organic fertilizers, zeolite and bio-liquid growth stimulant have provided potato yield with high flavor properties everywhere by increasing the content of starch (6.8-9.4 %) and vitamin C (1.6-3.0 mg%), while the similar doses of mineral fertilizers have increased the mentioned indices equally or very slightly.

3. In order to improve the ecological state of Lake Sevan, when organizing fertilization activities in the row crop fields cultivated in soil and climatic conditions of the lake basin, it is necessary to refuse mineral fertilizers and to apply organomix (10 t/ha) and biohumus (7 t/ha) instead, out of which 60 % should be introduced in the soil via seeding, 40 % - via nutrition; at the same time 3 t/ha zeolite should be applied in the soil and double foliar nutrition should be carried out with 5 l/ha application rate (with 500 l water). In the result of applying the recommended technology 400-420 c/ha high quality potato yield and 2026.5 thousand AMD extra profit is ensured.

4. Due to the applied technology, in conditions of irrigated agriculture in the Sevan basin 1300 m³/ha irrigation water has been saved, which will flow into Lake Sevan and its ecological state will be improved creating regular conditions for the growth and development of fauna and flora of the lake (by applying the mentioned technology in about 36 thousand ha irrigated areas, more than 50 mln m³ water will be saved annually, which will surely increase the lake water level and improve its ecological state).

5. The mentioned activities recommended upon the mentioned technology were subjected to production expertise in 2021 and approved on the example of 2 ha potato and cabbage fields cultivated in 22 farm households belonging to three communities (Artsvanist, Vardenik, Zolaqar) of the Sevan basin. Thus, in 2020 and further on, it is planned to completely introduce the mentioned technology in the irrigated agricultural system of the Sevan basin as a resource-saving and nature-friendly technology.

References

1. Dospekhov B.A. Field Experience Methodology – M. «Kolos», 1973.- 360 p
2. Galstyan M.H. Environmental biotechnologies. Textbook for HEIs, Yerevan, 2018- 300 p.
3. Galstyan M.H. Effectiveness of autumn wheat and potato fertilization in the conditions of Sevan basin – Yerevan, Limush, 2007 – 156p.
4. Galstyan M.A., Markosyan M.A., Matevosyan L.G., Hoveyan Z.H.//Economical-ecological efficiency of different dosages and application times of organomix and bio-liquid in the potato sowings under the conditions of Geghanist community, Masis region /Bulletin of National Agrarian University of Armenia, 2018, 4, p8-13.
5. Hayrapetyan E., Galstyan M., Harutyunyan S., Tamoyan S., The Eco-economic Efficacy of using Natural Mineral Ameliorants together with Organic Fertilizers for Eggplant Production // The biological Exhibit of Armenia Vol. LX,N3,2009,pp.82-87.
6. Hayrapetyan E.M., Shirinyan A.V. Agroecology. Textbook for AAU students: Yerevan. "Asoghik" publishing house, 2003.- 408 p.
7. Melqonyan K.G., Ghazaryan H.Gh., Manoukyan R.R. Current ecological state of agricultural lands, level of land use, improvement of management level and the ways of the effectiveness increase in the Republic of Armenia. Yerevan, The Scientific center of agrochemistry and melioration, 2004, 54 p.
8. Mineev V.G., Farming Chemization and Natural Environment.// Kolos, Moscow, 1990,172p.:
9. Yagodin B.A., Smirnov P.M., Peterburgski A.V. et al. Agro-chemistry (ed. by B.A. Yagodin), 2 edition, M. Agropromizdat., 1989, 639 p.
10. FAO-Annual fertilizer review, RAU, 2004.